

Cervical Cancer Screening in rural Tanzania: Retrospective Evaluation of Program Introduction in District Lindi

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Abstract

Considering the high rate of cervical cancer and the lack of comprehensive screening in Tanzania, the project aims to improve early detection and treatment to reduce disease-related deaths. The VIA technique was used. The screening was particularly well received by women aged 20 to 50 years. The VIA-positive findings were exclusively clinically detectable cervical carcinomas, which were immediately referred for oncological care. The results indicate that early detection has not been optimally implemented and suggest that the screening method should be reviewed, and the examiners retrained. Cervical cancer screening is increasingly being offered by local providers often supported by international NGOs. It is essential to collect and analyze data in a well-structured manner to ensure the reliability and effectiveness of cervical screening program in rural areas of Tanzania.

1. Introduction

Cervical cancer is a non-communicable disease that kills around 350,000 women worldwide every year (WHO, 2025). The WHO has called for the elimination of cervical cancer by 2030. Cervical cancer is caused by infection with the human papillomavirus (HPV), which is transmitted through sexual activity. Chronic HPV infection is considered carcinogenic and leads to changes in the cells of the squamous epithelium of the cervix. This can lead to precancerous stages of cervical carcinoma, which can develop into a cervical cancer after an average of four years. Visual inspection of the cervix with acetic acid (VIA) is an effective, low-cost screening method that can be performed by trained health workers. Peer reviews have shown a sensitivity of 66% and specificity of 87% for CIN2 (*WHO Web Annex B: Evidence to Decision Table*, 2021). A review from Runge et al. reported a cumulative VIA positivity rate of 9.2% (Runge et al., 2019). The VIA sensitivity can be increased if the examiners are experienced and receive supervision (Dartell et al., 2014).

Tanzania has the fourth highest cervical cancer rate in the world. The incidence and mortality were 34.3 % and 21.8 %, respectively in Tanzania (Sung et al., 2021). Cervical cancer remains a major public health problem in Tanzania and the most common type of cancer among women aged 15 to 44. There is no nationwide organized screening program (Mahiti et al., 2025). According to official figures, 10,241 cases of cervical cancer were diagnosed in Tanzania in 2021. 6,525 of these women died from the disease. HIV promotes the development of

cervical cancer. The prevalence of HIV among women in the Lindi region is 37.6% (Ministry of Health [Tanzania Mainland] et al., 2023). Women who have never been tested for HIV often have also never participated in cervical cancer screening (Hhera et al., 2025). A low level of formal education is associated with low socioeconomic status. The travel costs to attend cervical cancer screening at a health center are often unaffordable. In addition, women without formal schooling often have no knowledge about cervical cancer causes and development (Hhera et al., 2025). Different studies in Kenya (Gebreegziabher et al., 2024), (Tiruneh et al., 2017) showed that individuals with low or no formal education are often likely to be disadvantaged in comprehending reproductive educational content.

Early detection and treatment, especially of the preliminary stages of cervical cancer, can save women's lives. Tanzania lacks an official nationwide cervical cancer screening program. In addition, many women in Tanzania have a lack of knowledge about the development of cervical cancer and prophylactic HPV vaccinations, as well as the importance of screening tests (Henke et al., 2021). School education plays a crucial role in how well women are informed about cervical cancer and whether they consider having a cervical cancer screening test (Hhera et al., 2025). Local providers in rural areas Tanzania and other Sub-Saharan countries started to implement a cervical cancer screening often supported by NGOs. These efforts can be effective if they are accompanied by reliable data analysis. After screening, women go home knowing that they will not develop cervical cancer in the next three years. This assumes that cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) has already been detected. If reliable detection of precancerous stages cannot be achieved, the success of cervical cancer screening is at risk. In addition to high sensitivity for precancerous findings a well-designed follow up system is a crucial parameter that contributes to the success of a screening system. Lycke et al could show that after just two years, the risk of cervical cancer increases for untreated women with a CIN 2 lesion compared to women with a treated CIN lesion. The cumulative risk of cervical cancer increased in the active surveillance group at 2,5% after 20 years, whereas remained stable in the LLETZ group at 0,76%. Follow-up untreated CIN 2 is crucial for women (Lycke et al., 2023).

The project region of District Lindi is a rural area in south-eastern Tanzania. Medical treatment is unaffordable for a majority of the population. Only 20% of the local population has health insurance. In 2024, cervical cancer screening was introduced to address the serious shortcomings in the early detection and treatment of cervical cancer in the rural region of Lindi. The aim is to drastically reduce the number of serious illnesses in the region and prevent unnecessary deaths. Initially, medical staff such as ANOs and assistant doctors were trained in conducting structured screening examinations and documenting the data. The medical staff completed a comprehensive 7-day intensive training course. Digital data collection was carried out using a form based on the MTUHA Book 19. In the CTC (Care and Treatment Clinic) department of hospital, the VIA (Visual Inspection with Acetic Acid) examination is performed by a specialist nurse or doctor. Cervical cancer screening is part of the Community Health Program. The team regularly visits the surrounding villages in the region. In addition to the examination, women in remote areas receive various information about the causes of cervical cancer and what preventive measures are available.

2. Methode

2.1. Study design

A longitudinal study was conducted involving women who participated in VIA cervical cancer screening both in outreach and in hospital settings. This study accompanies the implementation phase of VIA-based cervical cancer screening in Lindi District. Data collection was carried out using KoboToolbox (www.kobotoolbox.org). KoboToolbox is an open source platform for collecting, managing, and visualizing data. An entry form based on MTUHA Book 19 was created in KoboToolbox for this purpose. The data was anonymised and taken from the MTUHA book.

2.2. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (Version 29.0.2.0, IBM). To test for differences between the two samples, Pearson-Chi-Square χ^2 -analyses and Phi-Cramer's V were used for dichotomous data. Differences in scores between groups were analyzed using *t*-test (two-tailed).

2.3. Setting and participants

The study collects all data during the first year of the cervical cancer screening. The cervical cancer screening took place during open consultation hours at the CTC department in the hospital and during visits as part of the community health program. The VIA method was used. The women got a screening pass and were invited to return for a follow-up examination in 3 years.

2.4. Statistical variables

The variables include the age, the number of deliveries, HIV status (positive, negative or unknown), VIA category (positive or negative) In this study, the further variable was whether a woman had ever screened for cervical cancer, which was a binary outcome coded as 'yes' for those who had ever been screened and 'no' otherwise.

3. Results

The data from 956 participants were evaluated. The average age was 42.11 years (SD 12,09). Cervical cancer screening targeted the risk group of women aged 20–49 (Figure 1). In Tanzania, cervical cancer is the most common cancer among women aged 15 to 44. reaching the high-risk group is a crucial success factor of cervical screening programmes. About 58,3% of the participants were at the high-risk group between 15 and 44 years 41,7% were older than 44 years old. The cervical cancer screening was carried out both in outreach as part of the community health program and in the CTC as an additional service. 69,7% of the women in total 664 were examined in the hospital's CTC and 22% in outreach setting. In 8.4% the venue of examination was missing.

Figure 1: Age of participants in cervical cancer screening

Of the 956 participants, 386 were HIV-positive, 480 were HIV-negative and 90 were HIV-unknown. The HIV prevalence of 40.38% was higher than the reported 37,6% prevalence from the official reporting of the Ministry of Health (Ministry of Health [Tanzania Mainland] et al., 2023). 376 HIV positive women were seen at the CTC versus 7 women in outreach. These women came to the HIV Consultation and were invited for cervical cancer screening. Women between the ages of 30 and 50 represented with 613 persons the largest group of participants. The 31 to 50 age group had the highest proportion of HIV positivity ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Bar chart HIV status and age group

The fertility rate averaged 3 children. The over-50 age group had a birth rate of 4.23 per woman. In the group of those over 60 and 70 years of age, the birth rate was 4.63 and 6.68 per woman, respectively (Figure 3).

Age group	Medium	N	SD
1 (15-20y)	0,48	21	0,512
2 (21-30y)	1,51	102	0,992
3 (31-40y)	2,80	205	1,284
4 (41-50y)	3,08	279	1,574
5 (51-60y)	4,23	88	2,227
6 (61-70y)	4,63	27	1,984
7 (>70y)	6,68	19	3,449
	3,00	741	1,914

Figure 3: Number of births and age group

In the cohort, 3.5% tested positive for VIA (Figure 4). These were 33 exclusively clinically detectable cervical carcinomas. The average age of women with positive VIA result was 48 years. 48.5% of positive screening results (16) were found in age group 41–50 years, followed by age group over 70 years with 21.2% positive (7) cases ($p < 0,001$). Within the age group 7 over years, a positive VIA result was most frequently recorded at 29.2% ($p < 0,001$). The youngest woman at the time of diagnosis was 19 years and the oldest 73 years old. The cohort included one case of clinical cervical cancer in who the screening result had been reported as negative in the past. This is exactly the kind of case that needs to be avoided.

Figure 4: VIA results

Cervical carcinoma was diagnosed in 6 participants with HIV-positive status, 24 participants with HIV-negative status and 3 with unknown HIV status. The study showed only a very weak correlation ($p = -0.07$) between HIV status and VIA positive findings. ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 5). However, HIV infection is a risk factor for cervical cancer, this could not be demonstrated in our cohort.

HIV Status	VIA Category			Total
	Negative	Not done	Positive	
Negative	454	2	24	480
Positive	380	0	6	386
Unknown	87	0	3	90
Total	921	2	33	956

Figure 5: Crosstabulation HIV Status and VIA Category

Most of the women 51,9 % have not had any cervical screening test in the past. 45,3% had a negative test. 0.9% of our cohort had a positive cervical screening test in the past (Figure 6)

VIA History			
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
negative	433	45,3	45,3
not done	496	51,9	51,9
positive	9	0,9	0,9
unknown	18	1,9	1,9
Total	956	100,0	100,0

Figure 6: Results of VIA in the history

4. Discussion

Tanzania still has a high birth rate. For Tanzania was in 2023 a global fertility rate (GFR) 138 of 1.000 women. Compared to 2000 the GFR decreased from 167 to 138 (Ahmed et al., 2025). In 2022, the fertility rate was 4.8 children per woman nationwide and in rural areas 5.5 children per woman was reported (Figure 7). In the Lindi District was 4.1 children per woman reported (Ministry of Health [Tanzania Mainland] et al., 2023, p 4). This poses major challenges for the country in terms of food security, health care and education. In our study groups, women under the age of 50 had fewer births on average than women over the age of 50.

Figure 7: Fertility rate Tanzania 1991-2022 (Ministry of Health [Tanzania Mainland] et al., 2023)

The new implemented cervical cancer screening using the VIA method was well received, and 70% of participants were from the 20–49 age group. One of the core targets of screening, meaning that the appropriate age group was reached. Informing and counselling women are important requirements in screening. During the cervical cancer screening program, both in the outreach program and in the hospital's outpatient clinic, women were informed about the development of cervical cancer and the possibility of HPV vaccination and were invited to return for a follow-up examination in three years. A detection rate of 3.5 % is rather low compared to international study results in LMICs. In many LMICs, the detection rate for VIA tests is between 5% and 15%. This depends on various factors, such as the experience of the examiner or the population. There was a high proportion of HIV-positive women (40,2%) in the study group. A higher rate of VIA-positive findings was expected. The low VIA sensitivity in the study cohort is associated with a high number of false negatives implying a large number of women with premalignant diagnosis are not diagnosed and thus not receiving proper treatment. The findings classified as VIA positive in our screening group were 33 clinically detectable cervical carcinomas. These women were immediately referred for further oncological care. The reason for the high prevalence of HIV in the region needs to be clarified. Participants with HIV-positive status did not show a higher prevalence of cervical carcinoma. No

precancerous lesion (CIN) was detected using the VIA method. The screening principle of early diagnosis and thus improvement of the individual prognosis has not yet been achieved. The data analysis helps to make quality-improving corrections here. It seems sensible to review the screening methods and retrain medical staff to improve the effectiveness of the program. The study does not collect data on the socio-economic status and education of the participants. The influence of education and household income cannot be determined.

5. Conclusion

The locally introduced cervical cancer screening using the VIA method has been well received, particularly by women in the risk group. The detection rate of 3,5 % is rather low compared to other countries in LMICs and indicates a need for improvement in training and methodology. The positive findings were exclusively clinically detectable cervical cancers. The screening has not yet optimally achieved the core requirement of early detection, why it is recommended that the methods be reviewed and the examiners retrained. The women were provided with comprehensive information about the development of cervical cancer, HPV vaccination and follow-up care. Overall, the study shows that when introducing cervical cancer screening in a rural context, continuous data collection and analysis is necessary to increase the effectiveness of the program. A follow-up system ensures that women with early cervical cancer can be detected and referred for oncological treatment.

Abbreviations

VIA – Visual Inspection with Acetic Acid

HIV – Human Immunodeficiency Virus

HPV – Human Papilloma Virus

CTC – Care and Treatment Clinic

MTUHA – Mfumo wa Taarifa za Uendeshaji wa Huduma za Afya

TDHS – Tanzania Demographic and Health Survey

TDHS-MIS – Tanzania Demographic and Health Survey and Malaria Indicator Survey

TRCHS – Tanzania Reproductive and Child Health Survey

CIN – Cervical Intraepitheliale Neoplasie

NGO – Non-governmental Organisation

LMIC – Low- and middle-income country

Table of figures

Figure 1: Age of participants in cervical cancer screening	4
Figure 2: Bar chart HIV status and age group	5
Figure 3: Number of births and age group	5
Figure 4: VIA Positivity	6
Figure 5: Crosstabulation HIV Status and VIA Category	6
Figure 6: Results of VIA in the history	6
Figure 7: Fertility rate Tanzania 1991-2022 (Ministry of Health [Tanzania Mainland] et al., 2023)	7

ETHICAL APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Human ethics and consent to participate declaration: not applicable

Participant consent was not required, as all analyses were based on completely anonymized data. The procedure followed the NATIONAL GUIDELINES FOR HEALTH DATA QUALITY ASSESSMENT TANZANIA (November 2016) and was monitored by the regional council health management team (C.H.M.T.).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data set is available from the corresponding author.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Study design, data analysis, and interpretation of results. Writing the manuscript, creating figures and tables. Ensuring reproducibility and compliance with ethical guidelines.

Timothy Kiula – Support with data collection.

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